

3D Printed Catheters in Organ Perfusion with respect to hemolysis

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Abstract: In the field of organ perfusion, the interface between organ and perfusion circuit is of vital importance for the success of perfusion. We have developed a 3D printing process to produce cost-effective and customized catheters. A parallel test process is used to verify effectiveness and safety. Thereby, individual process steps were iteratively optimized and verified. To demonstrate biocompatibility of these medical components, an experiment was conducted to evaluate hemolysis. Thereby, no increased hemolysis due to the 3D printed catheters could be detected. Future developments are aimed at automation of 3D printing process with in-process quality assurance.

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I. Introduction

In normothermic organ perfusion, the catheter as the interface between the organ and the tubing system of the perfusion circuit is vital for the supply of nutrients and a successful perfusion with subsequent transplantation. Conventional produced catheters with injection molding process are economic not suitable due to scalability and individuality of catheter combined with a small number of units. Restrictions on catheter sizes can result in organ undersupply or complicated surgical procedures.

In recent years, additive manufacturing technologies have been increasingly developed. The fields of application have been expanded from prototyping to series production. The use of 3D printing is also increasing in the field of medical technology, e. g. dental implants [1]. Additive manufacturing enables a high degree of individualization and is suitable for a small unit number. However, in 3D printing there are no applications for the management of blood, as in the field of normothermic perfusion.

The 3D printing process must be designed in the context of medical device development requirements. Additionally, special regulatory requirements for catheters according to ISO 10555-1 and biocompatibility within the application scenario according to ISO 10993-4 must be investigated in testing procedures. Special attention was paid to the safety of the catheters in terms of tightness and biocompatibility. Reproducibility is also necessary within the framework of the process. The aim of this study is to investigate the hemolytic properties as an aspect of biocompatibility of 3D-printed catheters using fused filament fabrication.

II. Material and Methods

We developed a concept of 3D printing and test process in context of medical technology. The developed process for 3D printed catheters is shown in figure 1. Starting from a catheter design based on CAD, the G-code is designed. The

control of this process step is vital for the later functionality based on the designed layer trajectories. Subsequently, the catheters are printed from PETG with VIVE Cube (VIVE-MedTech, Cottbus, Germany) under controlled process parameters, e. g. clean room conditions. Parameters, such as room and filament temperature as well as humidity, are controlled in the process to eliminate defects in body structure.

Figure 1: 3D printing and test process

Following this, the tightness of the catheters is tested in order to prove the safety for the subsequent application and has already been proven in a previous investigation [2]. If

errors were detected, the 3D printing and test process was passed again. In addition to proof that the materials used are chemically hemolysis, mechanical hemolysis due to the design was investigated.

For hemolysis testing a minimalized blood conditioning circuit (*nephroTOP*® perfusion circuit) with oxygenator (hilite 1000, Medos AG, Radeberg, Germany), gas supply (20 % O₂, 6 % CO₂, 74 % N₂) and reservoir (MVC 0730, Medos AG, Radeberg, Germany) was built up, see figure 2 [3]. Porcine blood from slaughterhouse process was collected, heparinized and decanted to citrated bottles and stored cold at 4 °C. A 3D printed catheter (5,7 mm outer diameter organ side/6,7 mm outer diameter perfusion circuit) was involved in blood line for 4 hours (Circuit A). For comparison, a comparative circuit (Circuit B) was equipped with a tubing connector, which is commonly used in organ perfusion (6,7 mm outer diameter from polycarbonate, Medos AG). Reference probes were taken before experiments from both perfusion circuits (Ref.). As worst case scenario of a catheter with the specified diameter, the perfusion flow was set to 800 ml/min. Blood gases and pH were set to physiological conditions (pH = 7,35-7,45, oxygen saturation=100 %, hematocrit = 18 %) measured with blood gas analyzer (ABL80 Basic, Radiometer GmbH, Krefeld, Germany). Temperature was set to (36 – 37) °C. Blood probes were taken every hour and used to calculate the plasma hemoglobin *c(PHb)* and total hemoglobin *c(Hb)* concentrations by cyanmethemoglobin method (hemoglobin (Hb), Bioanalytic GmbH, Umkirch/Freiburg, Germany). Thereby, an increase in plasma hemoglobin indicates hemolysis.

Figure 2: Perfusion circuit for hemolysis measurement

Hemolysis can be evaluated by hemolysis index. Due to the equivalence of both circuits (perfusion flow, volume, hematocrit), the following simplified index was chosen [4]:

$$HI = \frac{c(PHb) - c(PHb_{Ref})}{c(GHb)} * 100. \quad (1)$$

According to ASTM F756-00 (Standard Practice for Assessment of Hemolytic Properties of Materials) a sample with a hemolysis index of (0-2) % is classified as 'non-hemolytic', (2-5) % as 'weakly hemolytic' and > 5 % as 'hemolytic'.

III. Results and Discussion

We developed arterial and venous catheters for different organs with diameters ranging between (3 – 9,3) mm and different length ranging between (35 – 83) mm. The process was iteratively run through and parameter of G-code generation as well as machine parameters were optimized with regard to reproducibility.

Figure 3: Examination of hemolysis index in blood

The results of the hemolysis index of both circuits are comparable with a HI of 0,69 % (Circuit A) vs. 0,41 % (Circuit B) after 240 min (see fig. 3). The slightly increased values in Circuit A can be caused by the smaller inner diameter or the surface character. According to ASTM F756-00, the 3D printed catheter can therefore be classified as non-hemolytic in the context of a minimalized blood circuit. In the future, corresponding investigations must be performed in a larger group for all catheter sizes in order to verify the results.

IV. Conclusions

We have developed a 3D printing and test process for catheters within organ perfusion. This makes it possible to produce individual catheters cost-effectively while addressing safety and reproducibility requirements. Also, the hemolysis of 3D printed catheters could be demonstrated. Future developments are aimed at automation of the entire process and in-process quality assurance, e. g. by optical inspection of each printed layer. Additional investigations with regard to thrombosis must be carried out. Furthermore, the process can be applied to other individual medical devices.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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